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Abstract-Oral presentation

Methodology/Data: Remote sensing methods for characterising urban areas (multispectral, hyperspectral, SAR/InSAR, TIR, LiDAR), Multi-temporal approaches

Applications: Natural hazards, risk reduction and urban resilience

Exploitation of satellite data to evaluate Digital Twins of Coastal Urban Areas

Roberta Paranunzio¹, Beatrice Carlini¹, Elisa Adirosi¹, Sabina Angeloni¹, Andrea Rucci², Giovanni Serafino², Ivan Boscaino², Attilio Vaccaro², Luca Baldini¹

¹Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (ISAC), National Research Council (CNR), Italy; ²M.B.I. S.r.l, Pisa, Italy

Extreme weather events, sea level rise and coastal erosion are major issues that need to be urgently addressed in European coastal cities. Smart technologies can support Coastal Cities Living Lab (CCLLs) in detecting potential risky conditions in the study area and co-designing adaptation solutions, like Nature Based Solutions (NBS) and Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA). A GIS-based Early-Warning Support (EWS) system and Digital Twin (DT) platform presented here can be deployed in the CCLLs to assist both the planning of long-term climate resilience strategies and decision making in case of risky events. We show how the effectiveness of these solutions is evaluated by exploiting multi-temporal flood maps obtained from satellite in the coastal area of Massa (Italy). Specifically, we are developing a general analysis tool for testing outputs of hydraulic and hydrological models included in the DT exploiting synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images such as Sentinel-1 or COSMO-SkyMED, or optical imagery like Sentinel-2 available for major flood events in the study area in the last decade. Information on real case studies are retrieved by municipality report archives, Floods Directive maps, local newspapers and exploration of regional agencies website and Copernicus Services. Flood hazards maps in terms of flood extent and, wherever possible, water depth or flow velocities distributions, simulated by the models implemented in the DT will be thus compared to real flood events mapping and validated. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the procedure and solutions and their possible incorporation in environmental monitoring, early-warning systems, and decision-making processes at different CCLLs will be then assessed through meetings with relevant users. This work is supported by the project SCORE (Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities), funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003534.